

ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES VIS Á VIS STUDENTS' WORK PERFORMANCE: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Elementary School Teachers' Classroom Management Strategies Vis Á Vis Students' Work Performance: A Correlational Study

Honey Mae A. Cardines *

[For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.](#)

Abstract

Effective classroom management establishes a safe, structured, and conducive learning environment where learners can focus on learning. This study determined the elementary school teachers' classroom management strategies and students' performance at the identified schools of Malabuyoc District, Malabuyoc, Cebu for the school year 2023-2024 as a basis for a management plan. This study is anchored on B. F. Skinner's Theory of Behavior Modification and Lee and Marlene Canter's Assertive Discipline. This study used a descriptive-correlational research design which established the significant relationships of the variables in the study. A total of 84 respondents participated in the study. The significant relationship between the teacher respondents' profile years in teaching experience of 0.002 and relevant training and seminars attended to the extent of employment of Classroom Management strategies as perceived by themselves established a significant relationship of 0.043. The significant relationship between the Teacher Respondents' Profile such as the years of teaching experience and the Usefulness of the Classroom Management Strategies as perceived by themselves established a significant relationship of 0.003. The significant relationship between the Principal Respondents' Profile such as the relevant training and seminars attended and the extent of the teachers' employment of Classroom Management Strategies as perceived by the principals themselves established a significant relationship of 0.047. The significant difference between the Teachers' and Principals' Ratings Towards the Management Strategies revealed that there is no significant difference of 0.516 which accepts the null hypothesis. These findings are important to know what factors affect the utilization of classroom management strategies. With this, it is important to encourage all teachers to continue to explore effective management strategies that sustain quality teaching-learning experiences among learners.

Keywords: *classroom management strategies, teacher's work performance, descriptive correlational, management plan, malabuyoc*

Introduction

The process of the teaching-learning will never be completed without effective classroom management. It is an ongoing process of making a classroom conducive to learning. Managing a classroom is never an easy task since every learner is unique to handle (Lazarides et al., 2020). The learners can learn without the effective classroom management employed by the teachers (Wolf et al., 2021). The teachers' effectiveness reflects how a teacher manages the classroom (Obee et al., 2023). The kind of classroom management that the teacher is employing reflects her personality because it is closely related to teachers' professional competence and effectiveness (Koutrouba, 2020). Thus, there is a need to address classroom management for improved teaching-learning engagement inside the classroom setting.

There is no best strategy suited to all learners simply because every learner comes from different families, different upbringings, and different cultures (Lathifah et al., 2020) That is why there is a need to apply different classroom management strategies according to the ability of each learner. As an agent of change, teachers need to adapt to the behaviors of the learners while looking for the appropriate strategies that will suit the unique abilities of the children (Sprick et al., 2021). In any classroom that uses management techniques, pupils respond to compassionate teachers. As a result, it appears that the best classroom for children with varying requirements is one that is culturally sensitive and offers differentiation in teaching methods (Dees & Lacour, 2018).

According to research, many teachers are not fully prepared for any disruptive behaviors that children may bring to class, which creates issues for both teaching and learning (Flower et al., 2017). This is one of the most pressing issues where appropriate classroom management strategies should be constantly reviewed and studied. It cannot be denied that literature would speak on classroom management but because of the constant changes not just in the curriculum but also in the learner's learning needs in this generation, studying the elementary school teachers' classroom management strategies is of paramount in crafting management plan tailored to the specific district where this study will be conducted. Teaching is nothing without learning. The difficulty in handling diverse learners should be addressed because teacher's work performance can be affected by it (Franklin & Harrington, 2019). A standardized classroom observation method helps teachers evaluate their effectiveness and make development plans, which improves their preparation and proficiency (Barrogo, 2020).

The Professional Standards for Teachers incorporates the K-12 teacher quality standard, which includes the performance level of teachers in the classroom. Asio and Riego de Dios (2019) discussed some traits a professional instructor ought to have. The classroom observation tool is one of the Means of Verification (MOV) in the Results-Based Management System (RPMS) Portfolio. Thus, the more expert a teacher is in managing his/ her classroom the greater his rating is.

Employing classroom management strategies is important because it is not only the basis of a teacher's work performance but also ensures good quality of the teaching-learning process (Holzberger & Prestele, 2021). The way you operate your classroom has an immediate effect on both your ability to teach and your student's ability to learn (McGarr, 2021). It has an impact on a teacher's ability to convey knowledge as well as their ability to enjoy teaching. The achievement of pupils' academics is, by far, the most essential factor of all.

To ensure students' academic and social success, the importance of excellent classroom instruction and behavior control cannot be overstated. Despite solid empirical backing, essential tactics like as having clear goals and routines, providing precise feedback, and giving kids multiple chances to react are typically missing from educators' toolkits (Mitchell et al., 2017).

Through various classroom management strategies, the researcher believes that a teacher can create a positive learning environment as he/she teaches the learners effectively and efficiently. This inquiry determines the frequency and utility of classroom management techniques of identified elementary teachers of Malabuyoc District for the S.Y. 2023-2024 in proposing a management plan.

Research Questions

This research determined the elementary school teachers' classroom management strategies and students' performance at the identified schools of Malabuyoc District, Malabuyoc, Cebu, for the school year 2023-2024.

This study answered the following sub-questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to:
 - 1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.3. years of teaching experience;
 - 1.4. current position; and
 - 1.5. relevant training and seminars attended?
2. What is the student's level of performance?
3. To what extent are the teachers' frequency and usefulness of classroom management strategies as perceived by the teachers and their principal as to?
 - 3.1. behavior modification;
 - 3.2. assertive discipline;
 - 3.3. incentive method;
 - 3.4. reality therapy; and
 - 3.5. distinctive method?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondent's:
 - 4.1. profile and the extent of employment of classroom management strategies; and
 - 4.2. profile and the usefulness of the aforementioned strategies?
5. Is there a significant difference in the teacher's and principal's rating towards the management strategies?
6. What recommendations can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. This design establishes the significant relationship between the identified factors and variables that affect classroom management and students' work performance. The appropriate statistical treatment will be used in data analysis. Data will be tallied and interpreted to produce findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Participants

The total population of the study is illustrated in Table 1. As shown in the table, the respondents are categorized into three, small school, medium school, and big school. In small schools, there are 5 respondents from Calipay Elementary School 4 respondents from Palaypay Elementary School, and 4 respondents from Labrador Elementary School. In middle schools, there are 9 respondents from Looc Integrated School, 9 respondents from Calatagan Integrated School, and 7 respondents from Sorsogon Elementary School. In big schools, there are 11 respondents from Cerdeña Elementary School, 22 respondents from Malabuyoc, Central School, and 14 respondents from Montañeza Elementary School.

Instruments

This study adapted an instrument from Timtim (2019). Certain modifications were made by the researcher. The instrument went through the process of validation since changes were made following the steps followed by Cabello and Bonotan (2021). Face validity was conducted by the researcher to see the superficial relevance of the questions and their appropriateness. Content validity was done by experts in the fields of education, psychology, research, and evaluation. One expert is a doctor in educational management, another

expert is a master teacher with more than 12 years of experience, and another expert is a doctor in psychology and research and evaluation. The instrument gained a 0.81 score in its Cronbach's Alpha indicating a good score for reliability. With this, it can be concluded that the instrument is valid and reliable. This tool will be used to collect information about the frequency and utility of classroom management tactics. It provided the necessary information about Behavior Modification, Assertive Discipline, Incentive Method, Reality Therapy, and Distinctive Method.

Procedure

The researcher will seek permission from the school's principal where the study will be conducted. The informed consent was written in simple language and was elicited from the respondents before the administration of the questionnaire. Respondents are free to withdraw whenever they feel unsafe, uncomfortable, and for some personal reasons. The researcher will distribute the questionnaire, along with a cover letter, to the indicated respondents with the agreement of the School Head. Following the collection of all necessary data, the responses will be objectively totaled, examined, and interpreted, and conclusions will be reached. The information gathered from the respondents will be treated in the highest form of confidentiality.

Statistical Treatment

The frequency counts and percentages are to be used to determine the respondent's profile. The weighted mean and standard deviation are to be utilized to determine the frequency and usefulness of classroom management tactics. Pearson-product correlation will be utilized to determine the relationship between instructors' performance and the frequency and efficacy of classroom management strategies.

Results and Discussion

The manner of the data presentation is arranged according to what is indicated under the research question. The results and discussion are discussed with the corroboration of the literature to sustain the rigor of the study.

Table 1. *Age and Gender Profiles of the Teacher Respondents*

<i>Age Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
50 years old and above	18	24.00
40-49 years old	26	34.67
30-39 years old	25	33.33
29 and below	6	08.00
Total	75	100.00
<i>Gender Profile</i>		
Male	8	10.67
Female	67	89.33
Total	75	100.00

Table 1 presents the age and profile of the teacher respondents. It can be gleaned that with a total of 75 teacher respondents, 26 (34.67 %) are within the bracket of 40-49 years old, which is most of the sample, while 6 (8%) are within the bracket of 29 and below years old. This means that the teacher respondents are not young and are at the average level of tenure ranging from 30 to 50 years old. In terms of the teacher respondents' gender, most of them are female teacher respondents with 67 counts or 89.33 % while the male teacher respondents consist of 10.67 % or 8 counts. This means that most of the teachers are still being dictated by the norms of the society that teaching as a profession is a female option (Zawistowska, 2024).

The age and gender of the teacher respondents play a significant role in effectively utilizing classroom strategies (Tran & Do, 2022). Understanding the teacher respondents' age and gender can be of great help in making the lesson more interactive and engaging (Yoon, 2022). Age is one of the determining factors in teachers' level of experience and adaptability inside the classroom (Rasheed-Karim, 2020). Young teachers may be very idealistic in terms of handling the classroom due to their fresh knowledge of theories applicable to education while veteran teachers have more experience in managing the learners' behavior and attitude making it more productive in classroom discussion (Ahmad et al., 2020).

Gender, on the other hand, can also impact and influence the way how teacher respondents employ classroom management strategies (Kengatharan & Gnanarajan, 2023). Teachers' gender can influence how they communicate and interact with their learners and understand their learning needs (Xie & Derakhshan, 2021). Female teachers vary in how male teachers establish classroom authority and group dynamics (Liang et al., 2020). The kind of approach that female teachers use inside the classroom may differ from the way how male teachers connect with their students. With this, it is important to identify the teacher respondents' age and gender in addressing specific learning needs that can impact the learner's academic progress.

Table 2. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Teacher Respondents*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Doctorate	1	01.33
Master's Degree with Doctorate	1	01.33

Master's Degree	7	09.33
Bachelor's Degree with Master's unit	58	77.33
Bachelor's Degree	8	10.67
Total	75	100.00

Table 2 presents the highest educational attainment of the teacher respondents. Most of the teacher respondents are bachelor's degree holders with master's units having a count of 58 and a percentage of 77.33. One of the teacher respondents is a full-fledged doctor and one is a master's degree holder with doctoral units. This means that the teacher respondents are doing their best to continue or advance their graduate studies which they find a positive impact on their work and the academic performance of their learners (Valente et al., 2020).

When teachers pursue advanced education or pursue graduate education, they are oriented on how to deliver quality instruction anchored on evidence-based classroom management strategies and methods of teaching (Hart et al., 2023). This can help the learners to find meaning in what they are learning. Teachers with master's and doctoral units and degrees can offer a broader repertoire of instructional approaches, behavior management techniques, and appropriate classroom management strategies (Shernoff et al., 2021). This can pave the way to increase not just the learners' academic performance but also the teacher's work satisfaction especially in managing the disruptive behavior of the learners and thus, sustaining a conducive learning environment.

Table 3. *Years of Teaching Experience of the Teacher Respondents*

<i>Years of Teaching Experience</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
31 years and above	9	12.00
21-30 years	18	24.00
11-20 years	24	32.00
6-10 years	19	25.33
5 years and below	6	06.67
Total	75	100.00

Table 3 presents the teacher respondents' years of teaching experience. The number of years is counted on the first day that they practiced their profession. It can be gleaned that most of the teacher respondents rendered 11-20 years with a count of 24 (32%). Although it is in the bracket of 11-30 years of experience that most of the teachers are in, 6 teacher respondents have 5 years and below. This means that the teacher respondents are in the average number of years in terms of their teaching experience (Owens et al., 2020).

The teacher respondents' years of teaching experience significantly affect the way how they employ classroom management strategies in making the classroom conducive to learning (Abdullah, 2020). Their number of years in teaching provides them to enhance and hone their skills in teaching. This also provides them with a deeper understanding of the learner's behavior and attitude inside the classroom which can allow them to appropriately utilize effective classroom management strategies (Ahmed, 2024). Experienced teachers can distinguish which classroom management strategies can be used to address the most pressing issues inside the classroom especially learner's diversity and varying backgrounds (Wolf et al., 2021). These experienced teachers bring with them a repertoire of classroom management strategies that have been refined over the years (Potter, 2021). Having experience in teaching has advantages in securing a learning environment where learners gain the quality education they deserve.

Table 4. *Current Position of the Teacher Respondents*

<i>Current Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Master Teacher I	6	08.00
Teacher III	23	30.67
Teacher II	23	30.67
Teacher I	23	30.67
Total	75	100.00

Table 4 presents the current position of the teacher respondents. It can be seen that most of the teachers are Teacher I, II, and III with 23 counts (30.67%) each for a total of 69. There are only 6 teacher respondents who are master teachers. This data is clearly depicting that most of the teachers are working on their promotion. The numbers on the table suggest a fluid movement of promotion.

The current position of the teacher respondents is a manifestation that the Department of Education (DepEd), follows a ladder where teachers should acquire all the requirements to be promoted. As they obtain a higher position, it requires a higher level of responsibility (Rusilowati & Wahyudi, 2020). This means that there are teachers who are master teachers who perform more tasks and responsibilities than those teachers I to III. Connecting this to how they employ classroom management strategies underscores the fact that master teachers can help through their experience to mentor and coach young teachers (Sewell, 2021). Although young teachers may give an impressive level of energy and idealism inside the classroom, teachers with positions can help them grow more by balancing theories and practice. This can bring out the best in managing a classroom, especially in helping your teachers thrive in the profession.

Table 5. *Relevant Seminars and Training Attended by the Teacher Respondents*

<i>Relevant Seminars and Trainings Attended</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
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International	1	01.33
National	11	14.67
Regional	18	24.00
Local	45	60.00
Total	75	100.00

Table 5 presents the relevant seminars and training attended by the teacher respondents. It can be seen that most of the teachers attended local seminars and training relevant to their line of expertise with 45 counts (60%). Although it is very expensive to attend international training and seminars, one of the teachers made it through. This means that teachers can maximize opportunities in attending ways to improve themselves, personally and professionally, especially in how they can employ classroom management strategies effectively (Bawani & Mphahlele, 2021).

Attending relevant training and seminars can deepen one’s mastery in employing classroom management strategies wherein new valuable and helpful insights, current methodologies in this generation, and various teaching strategies are attained (Yakpo, 2021). This will make the classroom environment not just conducive to learning but can also increase the learners’ engagement time in learning the subject matter. Teachers are encouraged to always seek avenues where they can continue their professional growth and development (Buthelezi, 2021). This is embedded in the law to make sure that teachers are learning the latest pedagogical approaches, the kind of learners’ behavior propagating in this era, and how strategies are innovatively executed inside the classroom. The ultimate purpose is to address the challenging behavior of the learners and foster a positive learner-centered classroom.

Table 6 presents the age and gender profile of the principal respondents. It can be gleaned that of the 9 school principals, 4 of them are 50 years old and above and 2 of them are 40-49 years old. This can be implied that school principals in this district are having the stage of retiring from their calling to oversee the activities inside the school including the way how teachers are delivering quality instruction to the learners. For the gender, 5 of them are male and 4 of them are female. This means that they have almost equal number of male and female principals in the district (Chalikias et al., 2021).

Table 6. *Age and Gender Profile of the Principal Respondents*

<i>Age Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
50 years old and above	4	44.44
40-49 years old	2	22.22
30-39 years old	3	33.22
Total	9	100.00
<i>Gender Profile</i>		
Male	5	55.55
Female	4	44.44
Total	9	100.00

The principal respondents’ age and gender are vital in supporting and supervising the teachers’ classroom activities. Their ability to mentor, coach, guide, and influence the teacher’s teaching effectiveness can help address the challenges of implementing effective classroom management strategies (Hayes & Burkett, 2021). Older principals can offer a wide variety of classroom experiences and wisdom in handling learners’ disruptive behavior and other classroom challenges accumulated over time while newly installed school principals can give so much regarding the modern strategies and methodologies from their perspective (Karacabey, 2021). Their gender also plays a significant role in connecting and communicating with the teachers on how they will be molded and prepared to use effective classroom management strategies.

Table 7. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Principal Respondents*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Doctorate	1	11.11
Master's Degree	1	11.11
Bachelor's Degree with Master's unit	5	55.55
Bachelor's Degree	2	22.22
Total	9	100.00

Table 7 presents the highest educational attainment of the principal respondents. It can be gleaned that 5 of them or 55.55 % are bachelor’s degree holders with master’s units. Among the 9 school principals, one of them, or 11.11% is a full-fledged doctor and one is a full-fledged master. This implies that the school principal is not necessarily a full-fledged doctor as several criteria or qualifications may be considered to become a school administrator.

The school principal’s highest educational attainment can influence their instructional supervision of how teachers employ classroom management through their advanced educational backgrounds which enables them to provide nuanced support and guidance (Kartini et al., 2020). School principals can share their best knowledge and experience on how novel pedagogical practices are being applied inside the classroom especially to address the diversity of students and their attitudes and disruptive behavior. With the assistance of the school principal, teachers received the best help they could get in creating a sportive and effective learning environment for the

learners and the teachers. This is where both can grow together.

Table 8. *Years of Teaching Experience of the Principal Respondents*

<i>Years of Teaching Experience</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
31 years and above	2	22.22
21-30 years	3	33.33
11-20 years	2	22.22
6-10 years	2	22.22
Total	9	100.00

Table 8 presents the years of teaching experience of the principal respondents. It can be gleaned that 3 school principals have 21-30 years of experience while the rest of the school principals are within the 6-10 years, 11-20 years, and 31 years and above bracket of years of teaching experience. This means that school principals have varying lengths of experience and can provide different techniques, approaches, methods, and strategies in employing classroom management best practices (Malonza, 2020).

The school principals' years of teaching experience impact the lives of the teachers in employing classroom management strategies (Sichon & Guhao, 2020). The years spent in teaching generated a wide array of varying situations of learners' attitudes and behavior inside the classroom (Ezeanolue & Nwankwo, 2020). The direct purposeful learning experiences of the school principals are a contributory factor that they can give practical pieces of advice and techniques for improving the way how teachers handle various challenges in the classroom.

Table 9. *Current Position of the Principal Respondents*

<i>Current Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Principal II	1	11.11
Principal I	3	33.33
Head Teacher III	2	22.22
Head Teacher II	2	22.22
Head Teacher I	1	11.11
Total	9	100.00

Table 9 presents the current position of the principal respondents. It can be gleaned that out of 9 school principals, there are 3 (33.33%) who are Principal I and 1 (11.11%) of them is Principal II. The rest are head teachers. This implies that the data is well distributed which can give a better position and quality discussion as to how Head Teacher versus School Principal provides their way of guiding and helping the teachers in terms of employing effective classroom management strategies (Saleem et al., 2020).

School principals are the ones who establish a good atmosphere inside the school as the teacher sets the tone inside the classroom (Ariyani & Zuhaery, 2021). The way school principals are managing their instructional duties and supervision tasks would reflect on how teachers are managing their classrooms. The current position of the school principal provides them the means of establishing assistance on how teachers can get instructional help and guidance especially those who are new in the profession (Ryu et al., 2022). The overall influence of the school principal can be felt by the teachers not just in how they employ innovative classroom management strategies but also in creating a psychological climate contributing to a positive learning environment.

Table 10. *Relevant Seminars and Training Attended by the Principal Respondents*

<i>Relevant Seminars and Trainings Attended</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
National	2	22.22
Regional	4	44.44
Local	3	33.33
Total	9	100.00

Table 10 presents the relevant seminars and training attended by the principal respondents. 4 of them (44.44%) attended regional seminars and training while 2 of them (22.22%) attended national seminars and training. This implies that school principals are actively involved in national and regional seminars and training. The common perception about this is that, whether one attends international or national seminars, the transfer of knowledge would still be the same, especially in education (Iftikhar et al., 2022).

In fostering quality mentorship, school principals are given the obligation to observe classes and provide constructive criticisms that can be impactful in helping classroom teachers grow and thrive personally and professionally (Abelang et al., 2020). The knowledge gained from the seminars and training can be shared and applied in managing the teachers through the implementation of effective classroom management strategies (Simonsen et al., 2020). The supportive efforts of the school principals will not just help the teachers but also improve the engagement time of the learners and increase the learners' academic performance.

Table 11. *The Student's Level of Performance*

<i>Transmuted Grade Range</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
90 – 100	Outstanding (5)	30	21.89%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory (4)	35	25.55%

80 – 84	Satisfactory (3)	37	27.01%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory (2)	13	9.49%
74 & below	Did Not Meet Expectations (1)	22	16.06%
Mean Grade =	Satisfactory (3.06)	Total = 137	100%

Table 11 presents the student’s level of performance. It can be gleaned that the students' mean grade is satisfactory with a transmuted grade range from 80 to 84. This means that the students in the study are average. With a total sample of 137, 37 of them, or 27.01% had a satisfactory grade which garnered the highest count. In contrast, 13 of them, or 9.49% landed on fairly satisfactory grades ranging from 75 to 79. It can be implied that the data has well-distributed or dispersed counts in terms of their academic performance (Owusu et al., 2021).

Student performance is vital to how teachers manage the classroom in a way that provides the best conditions where they can learn and experience the quality education they deserve (Adedigba & Sulaiman, 2020). The academic performance of the students can be a good reference as an outcome of the teacher’s employment of the classroom management strategies’ usefulness and the number of times that these strategies are being utilized (Ahmed, 2024). The effort and dedication of the teacher and how effective they are in using these classroom management strategies can be manifested on how organized their classrooms are and the kind of behavior that their students are showing inside the classroom.

Table 12. *Extent of the Teachers’ Frequency of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Behavior Modification as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Behavior Modification Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The Teacher... gives points to students who consented to a given assignment.	4.52	Always	4.33	Often
2. utilizes group rewards for groups that complete a task early. (For example, points, playtime privilege)	4.01	Often	4.00	Often
3. creates a personal reward program (e.g., stickers, awards).	3.65	Often	3.33	Sometimes
4. sends text or use social media account or talk personally to the parents if the child shows desirable behavior.	4.31	Often	4.56	Always
5. celebrates desirable behavior through clapping hands and other methods of praising that will make the child recognizable.	4.61	Always	4.22	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	4.22	Often	4.09	Often

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00 = Always; 3.51 – 4.50 = Often; 2.51 – 3.50 = Sometimes; 1.51 – 2.50 = Rarely; 1.00 – 1.50 = Never

Table 12 presents the Extent of the Teachers’ Frequency of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Behavior Modification as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals. It can be gleaned that the overall weighted mean under the teacher respondents is 4.22 with a verbal interpretation of Often while 4.09 under the principal respondents who rated the teachers’ way of employing the behavior modification (Zoromski et al., 2021).

Among the statements under this classroom management strategy for the teacher’s extent of frequency, the statement, “celebrates desirable behavior through clapping hands and other methods of praising that will make the child recognizable” gained the highest weighted mean of 4.61 while the statement, “creates a personal reward program (e.g., stickers, awards)” obtained the lowest mean of 3.65. This means that teachers are encouraging and motivating their learners to do their best through clapping of hands and other gestures so that the learners feel that they are being recognized (Yassine et al., 2020). The personal reward program is not usually manifested inside the classroom.

As validated by the principal respondents, the statement, “sends text or use social media account or talk personally to the parents if the child shows desirable behavior” gained the highest mean of 4.56 while the same with the teachers, the statement, “creates a personal reward program (e.g., stickers, awards)” garnered the lowest mean. School principals observed that teachers are highly connected to their parents, especially in raising concerns on desirable and undesirable behaviors (Khan & Uzair-ul-Hassan, 2021). This paves the way to prevent the teachers from imposing consequences as a product of the learners’ consequences.

Table 13. *The extent of the Teachers’ Frequency of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Assertive Discipline as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Assertive Discipline Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. does not allow disobedient students to continue without applying disciplinary measures.	4.39	Often	4.11	Often
2. will not allow a student to block learning from a student who shows willingness to learn.	4.40	Often	4.44	Often
3. constantly encourages children to reach their greatest potential by participating in an activity that will help them develop their talents.	4.75	Always	4.56	Always
4 constantly compliments students who demonstrate modeled and replicable behavior by permitting the recognized students to stand and the remaining students will clap	4.55	Always	4.78	Always

their hands.				
5. constantly reminds students about classroom rules and regulations and instills the importance of following them.	4.64	Always	4.78	Always
Overall Weighted Mean	4.55	Always	4.53	Always

Table 13 presents the extent of the teachers’ frequency of employment of classroom management strategies in terms of Assertive Discipline as perceived by the teachers and principals. It can be seen in the table that the overall mean as perceived by the teacher respondents is 4.55 interpreted as Always while 4.53 with the same interpretation as perceived by the principal respondents. This means that teachers and principals almost have a common perception regarding assertive discipline being employed inside the classroom (Thilagaratman & Yamat, 2021).

From the perspective of the teachers and among the statements under Assertive Discipline, the statement, “constantly reminds students about classroom rules and regulations and instills the importance of following them” garnered the highest mean of 4.64 while the statement, “does not allow disobedient students to continue without applying disciplinary measures” gained the lowest mean of 4.39. This means that teacher respondents believed that when learners are reminded about the classroom rules and regulations and why they need to follow those, the classroom can be managed well (Omeri & Dervishi, 2022).

From the perspective of the principal respondents, the statements, “constantly compliments students who demonstrate modeled and replicable behavior by permitting the recognized students to stand and the remaining students will clap their hands” and “constantly reminds students about classroom rules and regulations and instills the importance of following them” generated the highest mean of 4.78 while the statement, “does not allow disobedient students to continue without applying disciplinary measures” gained the lowest mean of 4.11. This means that school principals observe teachers consistently giving praise to those students who portray positive behavior (Maponya, 2020). School principals notice that teachers are not imposing so much of disciplinary measures because the classroom is already managed in a way that learners understand the importance of following rules and regulations.

Table 14. *Extent of the Teachers’ Frequency of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Incentive Method as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Incentive Method Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. employs a hand signal to instruct students to behave or to cease doing things that are unneeded.	4.33	Often	3.33	Sometimes
2. uses exceptional incentives (e.g., special helper, additional playtime)	3.68	Often	3.22	Sometimes
3. allows students enjoy early recess or break time when the pupils finish a work or test early.	4.04	Often	3.33	Sometimes
4 allows an advanced student to assist a sluggish learner, particularly on an exam	3.76	Often	2.89	Sometimes
5. allows the group who is behind of the activity to complete it despite the fact that they did not win.	4.36	Often	3.56	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	4.03	Often	3.27	Sometimes

Table 14 presents the extent of the teachers’ frequency of employment of classroom management strategies in terms of the Incentive Method as perceived by the teachers and principals. It can be seen that the overall weighted mean under the teacher’s perception is 4.03 and interpreted as often, while 3.27 overall weighted mean interpreted as sometimes under the perception of the principal. This means that the teacher respondents and principal respondents have varying standpoints concerning the how incentive method is being utilized inside the classroom (Assibey, 2021).

The teacher respondents perceived that among all the statements, the statement, “allows the group who is behind of the activity to complete it even though they did not win” garnered the highest mean of 4.36 while the statement, “uses exceptional incentives (e.g., special helper, additional playtime)” gained the lowest mean of 3.68. This implies that teachers gave chances to the learners who were doing their best to complete the academic task despite having the losing end (HD & Darmawan, 2023). This can help the learners to appreciate more what they accomplish not what they get after accomplishing the task.

The principal respondents perceived that among all the statements, the statement, “allows the group who is behind of the activity to complete it even though they did not win” gained the highest mean of 3.56 and the statement that gained the lowest mean of 2.89 the statement, “allows an advanced student to assist a sluggish learner, particularly on an exam”. This means that although the overall weighted mean between the teacher respondents and principal respondents varies, the highest mean among all the statements is the same (Chen et al., 2020). The observation and the perception of the teacher respondents and principal respondents are in parallel.

Table 15. *Extent of the Teachers’ Frequency of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Reality Therapy as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Reality Therapy Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1 educates pupils to always do right for others.	4.84	Always	4.89	Always
2. always advises students to avoid bullying because it has a negative	4.83	Always	4.56	Always

impact on the students who are bullied.				
3. inculcates students to be in the company of people who nourish their talents and serve as a positive role model for good deeds.	4.56	Always	4.33	Often
4 urges students to take part in classroom discussions or any collaborative activities that contribute to lifetime learning.	4.61	Always	4.44	Often
5. informs the parents about their child's abilities and progress, during homeroom meetings.	4.83	Always	4.56	Always
Overall Weighted Mean	4.73	Always	4.56	Always

Table 15 presents the extent of the teachers’ frequency of employment of classroom management strategies in terms of Reality Therapy as perceived by the teachers and principals. It can be gleaned that the overall weighted mean under the teachers’ perception is 4.73 and interpreted as always while 4.56 with the same interpretation under the principal respondents’ perception. This gives the impression that in reality therapy, school principals validated well with correctness of how teachers perceived it in terms of utilization inside the classroom.

Anchoring the teacher respondents’ perception, the statement under reality therapy that garnered the highest mean of 4.84 is the statement, “educates pupils always to do right for others”. In contrast, the lowest mean of 4.56 is the statement, “inculcates students to be in the company of people who nourish their talents and serve as a positive role model for good deeds”. This implies that teachers perceive reality therapy as a classroom management strategy that educates the learners to do what is right and to choose the highest good (Sarpourian et al., 2022).

The principal respondent’s perception of reality therapy can be determined through how they observe the teachers. The statement, “educates pupils always to do right for others” garnered the highest mean of 4.89. In contrast, the statement, “inculcates students to be in the company of people who nourish their talents and serve as a positive role model for good deeds” gained the lowest weighted mean of 4.33. This means that the perception of the teacher respondents coincides with the principal respondents’ perception having the same statements for the highest and lowest weighted mean. Further, this implies that the principal respondents are also crucial in terms of how teachers should inculcate the value of doing what is right (Kaso, 2021).

Table 16. *Extent of the Teachers’ Frequency of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies in Terms of Distinctive Method as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Distinctive Method Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. urges students to be vigilant, disciplined, and cooperative when participating in group activities in order to win.	4.56	Always	4.56	Always
2. as a role model for students, he/she makes every effort to continue performing good deeds that students might admire and imitate.	4.73	Always	4.56	Always
3. handles students fairly and equally, whenever the necessity arises.	4.76	Always	4.67	Always
4 talks to the student personally if the student requires assistance and comfort.	4.68	Always	4.56	Always
5. explicates to the students why he/she gets irritated in certain situations, particularly when a student is misbehaving.	4.40	Often	3.67	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	4.63	Always	4.40	Often

Table 16 shows the extent of the teachers’ frequency of employment of classroom management strategies in terms of the Distinctive Method as perceived by the teachers and principals. It can be gleaned that the overall mean of the teacher respondents’ perception is 4.63 which is interpreted as Always and 4.40 for the principal respondents’ perception. This implies that teacher respondents are using this classroom management strategy most of the time as they want to recognize the potential of their students (Lazarides et al., 2020).

Under the perception of the teacher respondents, the statement that garnered the highest mean of 4.76 is that “The teachers handle students fairly and equally, whenever the necessity arises” and the lowest mean of 4.40 was garnered by the statement, “The teacher explicates to the students why he/she gets irritated in certain situations, particularly when a student is misbehaving”. This means that teachers value the students equally and provide them with an atmosphere where biases do not exist (Gilmour et al., 2022; van Driel et al., 2021). With the perception of the principal respondents, among the statements in a distinctive method, the statement, “The teachers handle students fairly and equally, whenever the necessity arises” gained the highest mean of 4.67 while the statement, “The teacher explicates to the students why he/she gets irritated in certain situations, particularly when a student is misbehaving” garnered the lowest mean of 3.67. The same with the teachers, the school principal observed that teachers are treating the learners fairly and equally. This means that in terms of employing distinctive methods inside the classroom, having equal treatment would always be manifested as this is one of the sources of conflict that may ruin classroom management (Valente et al., 2020).

Table 17. *Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Behavior Modification as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Behavior Modification Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI

1. The Teacher... gives points to students who consented to a given assignment.	4.40	Often	4.56	Always
2. utilizes group rewards for groups that complete a task early. (For example, points, playtime privilege)	4.05	Often	4.11	Often
3. creates a personal reward program (e.g., stickers, awards).	3.76	Often	3.67	Often
4. sends text or use social media account or talk personally to the parents if the child shows desirable behavior.	4.31	Often	4.44	Often
5. celebrates desirable behavior through clapping hands and other methods of praising that will make the child recognizable.	4.48	Often	4.11	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	4.20	Often	4.18	Often

Table 17 presents the Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Behavior Modification as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals. It reveals that the overall weighted mean is 4.20 for the teacher respondents’ usefulness with an interpretation of often and 4.18 for the principal respondents’ usefulness with the same interpretation. This means that in using behavior modification as a classroom management strategy, the practices or statements are not always used or manifested in the delivery of quality instruction (Stevenson et al., 2020; Zoromski et al., 2020).

With the perception of the teacher respondents in the utilization of behavior modification strategy inside the classroom, the statement, “The teacher celebrates desirable behavior through clapping hands and other methods of praising that will make the child recognizable” garnered the highest mean of 4.48 while the statement, “The teacher creates a personal reward program (e.g., stickers, awards)” gained the lowest mean of 3.76. This means that teacher respondents use this classroom strategy to celebrate the desirable behavior of the learners (Beahm et al., 2021; Backfisch et al., 2021).

As validated by the principal respondents regarding the usefulness of the behavior modification strategy, the highest mean of 4.56 is gained by the statement, “The teacher gives points to students who consented to a given assignment” while the statement, “The teacher creates a personal reward program (e.g., stickers, awards)” garnered the lowest mean of 3.67. This means that principal respondents view the usefulness of behavior modification as being used by the teachers in a way that when students are doing their assignments (Janakiraman et al., 2021), they are given assigned points that can motivate them to fulfill their homework (Hang & Van, 2020; Aura et al., 2021).

Table 18. *Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Assertive Discipline as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Assertive Discipline Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. does not allow disobedient students to continue without applying disciplinary measures.	4.29	Often	4.22	Often
2. will not allow a student to block learning from a student who shows willingness to learn.	4.23	Often	4.44	Often
3. constantly encourages children to reach their greatest potential by participating in an activity that will help them develop their talents.	4.64	Always	4.67	Always
4 constantly compliments students who demonstrate modelled and replicable behavior by permitting the recognized students to stand and the remaining students will clap their hands.	4.47	Often	4.67	Always
5. constantly reminds students about classroom rules and regulations and instills the importance of following them.	4.56	Always	4.78	Always
Overall Weighted Mean	4.44	Often	4.56	Always

Table 18 shows the Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Assertive Discipline as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals. The overall weighted mean for the teacher respondents’ perception of the usefulness of the assertive discipline strategy is 4.44 and interpreted as often while 4.56 with the interpretation of always is the overall weighted mean for the principal respondents’ perception of the strategy’s usefulness. This means that principal respondents are seeing the usefulness of assertive discipline in the classroom which paves the way to help the learners develop self-discipline (Kimanzi, 2022; Shaheen et al., 2020).

As to the perception of the teacher respondents in the usefulness of assertive discipline, it can be gleaned that the statement, “The teacher constantly reminds students about classroom rules and regulations and instills the importance of following them” garnered the highest mean of 4.78 while the statement, “The teacher does not allow disobedient students to continue without applying disciplinary measures” gained the lowest mean of 4.22. This means that teacher respondents are particular in reminding and instilling in the learners the classroom rules and regulations and the importance of why these are being followed (Jeruto et al., 2021). With this, the teachers will have less in terms of classroom management challenges.

As to the perception of the principal respondents’ usefulness of assertive discipline, it can be gleaned that the statement, “The teacher constantly reminds students about classroom rules and regulations and instills the importance of following them” gained the highest mean of 4.78 while the statement, “The teacher does not allow disobedient students to continue without applying disciplinary measures”

garnered the lowest mean of 4.22. This implies that the principal respondents observed how teachers are consistent in terms of reminding the learners regarding the rules and regulations agreed upon inside the classroom and the rationale of why everyone must follow them (Edward, 2021).

Table 19 presents the Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Incentive Methods as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals. The overall weighted mean for the teacher respondents’ perception of the usefulness of the incentive method is 4.01 which is interpreted as often while 3.47 with the interpretation of sometimes is the overall weighted mean for the principal respondents’ perception of the strategy’s usefulness. This means that the validation of the school principal is lower than that of the perception of the teacher respondents which can imply that teachers usually do not utilize incentive methods as a classroom management strategy (Nagro et al., 2019; Khoirunnisak et al., 2023).

Under the perception of the teacher respondents in the usefulness of the incentive method, the statement gained the highest mean of 4.29 which is “The teacher employs a hand signal to instruct students to behave or to cease doing things that are unneeded” can provide a clear understanding that teachers are utilizing hand signal or gestures to control the students’ activities. The statement that garnered the lowest mean of 3.77 states that “The teacher allows an advanced student to assist a sluggish learner, particularly on an exam” is not usually being practiced as this can create biases. Advanced learners may compromise academic tasks and activities that are essential for their growth because even if the learner is advanced, the learner has specific needs (Goodyear & Carvalho, 2019; Chen, 2023).

Table 19. *Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Incentive Method as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

<i>Incentive Method Statements</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Principals</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. employs a hand signal to instruct students to behave or to cease doing things that are unneeded.	4.29	Often	3.78	Often
2. uses exceptional incentives (e.g., special helper, additional playtime)	3.69	Often	3.44	Sometimes
3. allows students enjoy early recess or break time when the pupils finish a work or test early.	4.04	Often	3.56	Often
4. allows an advanced student to assist a sluggish learner, particularly on an exam	3.77	Often	3.00	Sometimes
5. allows the group who are behind of the activity to complete it despite the fact that they did not win.	4.24	Often	3.56	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	4.01	Often	3.47	Sometimes

Under the perception of the principal respondents on the usefulness of the incentive method, it can be gleaned that the statement having the highest mean of 3.78 which states “employs a hand signal to instruct students to behave or to cease doing things that are unneeded” resembles the perception of the teacher respondents. The statement has the lowest mean of 3.00 which states that “The teacher allows an advanced student to assist a sluggish learner, particularly on an exam” which aligns with what the teacher respondents perceived. This implies that the validation of the principal respondents has a congruent observation and manifestation (Cheon et al., 2020).

Table 20 presents the Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Reality Therapy as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals. It can be seen that the teacher respondents’ perception of the usefulness of reality therapy has an overall weighted mean of 4.63, interpreted as always, and 4.53 for the perception of the principal respondents. This implies that principals can observe how teachers are utilizing reality therapy as a classroom management strategy (Alalwan et al., 2020).

Under the perception of the teacher respondents, the statement that garnered the highest mean of 4.72 is the statement, “The teacher informs the parents about their child’s abilities and progress, during homeroom meetings” and the statement that garnered the lowest mean of 4.55 is “The teacher urges students to take part in classroom discussions or any collaborative activities that contribute to lifetime learning”. Teachers and parents should help one another in providing the best education to all learners. Collaborative efforts from the teachers to connect to the parents in terms of their academic progress are vital for monitoring purposes. Reality therapy can be achieved not just by allowing learners to see the nature of their reality and behavior but also by immersing them in the world and how they can thrive (Asad et al., 2021).

Table 20. *Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Reality Therapy as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

<i>Reality Therapy Statements</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Principals</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1 educates pupils to always do right for others.	4.71	Always	4.67	Always
2. always advises students to avoid bullying because it has a negative impact on the students who are bullied.	4.71	Always	4.67	Always
3. inculcates students to be in the company of people who nourish their talents and serve as a positive role model for good deeds.	4.47	Often	4.56	Always
4 urges students to take part in classroom discussions or any collaborative activities that contribute to lifetime learning.	4.55	Always	4.44	Often
5. informs the parents about their child’s abilities and progress, during homeroom meetings.	4.72	Always	4.33	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	4.63	Always	4.53	Always

With the perception of the principal respondents, two statements gained the highest mean of 4.67 and these are “The teacher educates

pupils to always do right for others” and “The teacher always advises students to avoid bullying because it has a negative impact on the students who are bullied” while the lowest mean of 4.33 is garnered by the statement “The teacher informs the parents about their child's abilities and progress, during homeroom meetings”. This means that principals’ perception of how teachers are employing reality therapy is more focused on the teachers’ way of educating the learners to do what is right and how to avoid one of the most pressing issues in the educational realm and that is bullying (Davidoff & Shapira-Lishchinsky, 2020; Villar et al., 2022).

Table 21 shows the Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Distinctive Methods as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals. It can be gleaned that the overall weighted mean of the teacher respondents’ perception of the usefulness of the Distinctive Method is 4.55 which is interpreted as always. In contrast, the principal respondents’ perception has an overall weighted mean of 4.45 and is interpreted as often. This means that teacher respondents always believed that distinctive methods are useful in classroom management (Sanger, 2020; Delbo et al., 2023).

With the perception of the teacher respondents, the statement that garnered the highest mean of 4.67 is “The teacher handles students fairly and equally, whenever the necessity arises” while the statement that gained the lowest mean of 4.35 is “The teacher explicates to the students why he/she gets irritated in certain situations, particularly when a student is misbehaving”. This means that teacher respondents use distinctive methods in handling the learners fairly and equally (Gomez et al., 2024; Arellano et al., 2024).

Table 21. *Extent of the Usefulness of the Teachers’ Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Distinctive Method as Perceived by the Teachers and Principals*

Distinctive Method Statements	Teachers		Principals	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. urges students to be vigilant, disciplined, and cooperative when participating in group activities in order to win.	4.51	Always	4.56	Always
2. as a role model for students, he/she makes every effort to continue performing good deeds that students might admire and imitate.	4.65	Always	4.56	Always
3. handles students fairly and equally, whenever the necessity arises.	4.67	Always	4.56	Always
4 talks to the student personally if the student requires assistance and comfort.	4.56	Always	4.44	Often
5. explicates to the students why he/she gets irritated in certain situations, particularly when a student is misbehaving.	4.35	Often	4.11	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	4.55	Always	4.45	Often

With the perception of the principal respondents, the statements that gained the highest mean of 4.56 are “The teacher urges students to be vigilant, disciplined, and cooperative when participating in group activities to win”, “The teacher as a role model for students, he/she makes every effort to continue performing good deeds that students might admire and imitate”, and “The teacher handles students fairly and equally, whenever the necessity arises”. These three statements are what the school principals observe among their teachers in terms of using the Distinctive Method as a classroom management strategy. The statement that gained the lowest mean of 4.11 is “The teacher explicates to the students why he/she gets irritated in certain situations, particularly when a student is misbehaving”. This means that most of the statements under this strategy are what the school principals see during their instructional supervision to their teachers on how it is being employed inside the classroom (Honig & Rainey, 2019; Cabello et al., 2021).

Table 22. *Significant Relationship between the Student’s Level of Performance and the Extent of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies*

Variables	Computed t-test value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Level of Students’ Performance Teachers’ Extent of Classroom Management Strategies	-0.150	0.202	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 23 reveals the significant relationship between the teacher respondents’ profile and the extent of employment of Classroom Management strategies as perceived by themselves. Two indicators from the respondent’s demographic profile such as the years of teaching experience with a p-value of 0.002 and relevant training and seminars attended with a p-value of 0.043 established a significant relationship. The rest of the indicators such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, and current teaching position established no significant relationship. This implies that in employing classroom management strategies, it takes years of teaching experience and relevant training and seminars to help the teachers utilize these strategies (Mireles-Rios et al., 2019; Segarino et al., 2022).

Table 23. *Significant Relationship between the Teacher Respondents’ Profile and the Extent of Employment of Classroom Management Strategies as Perceived by Themselves*

Profiles	Computed r-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	0.170	0.144	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Gender	0.152	0.192	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.163	0.163	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Years In Teaching Experience	0.988	0.002	Reject Ho	Significant

Current Position	0.119	0.308	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Relevant Training and Seminars Attended	0.234	0.043	Reject Ho	Significant

The ultimate intent of how to make a classroom environment conducive to learning is when different classroom management strategies are frequently utilized to address the specific needs of the learners. Learners have varying learning needs depending on factors existing inside the classroom (Wong, 2023). It is important to identify these challenges and augment them by using appropriate classroom management techniques and pedagogical approaches. The demographic profile of the teacher respondents is considered one of the factors that affect the way how teachers use different classroom management strategies effectively (Strelow et al., 2020; Catulpos et al., 2024).

Table 24 shows the significant relationship between the Teacher Respondents' Profile and the Usefulness of the Classroom Management Strategies as perceived by themselves. It can be gleaned that only the years of teaching experience established a significant relationship with a p-value of 0.003 to the usefulness of the classroom management strategies. The rest of the indicators such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, current teaching position, and the relevant training and seminars attended established no significant relationship. This means that to maximize the usefulness of these classroom management strategies, one should have several years of teaching (Wolff et al., 2021; Ancot et al., 2023).

Table 24. *Significant Relationship between the Teacher Respondents' Profile and the Usefulness of the Classroom Management Strategies as Perceived by Themselves*

Profiles	Computed r-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	0.186	0.111	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Gender	0.162	0.166	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.213	0.067	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Years In Teaching Experience	0.981	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
Current Position	0.106	0.367	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Relevant Training and Seminars Attended	0.111	0.345	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Experience is the best teacher, and teachers embrace this reality in the corners of the classroom (Patterson & Han, 2019). Gaining experience is imperative in the teaching profession as this serves as a ticket to attaining practical knowledge and skills that theory cannot give (Jacob et al., 2020). The data above provided a realization of the importance of having teaching experiences. Experience can foster personal and professional growth especially in facing varying challenges inside the classroom and dealing with diverse learners (Franklin & Harrington, 2019).

Table 25. *Significant Relationship between the Principal Respondents' Profile and the Extent of the Teachers' Employment of Classroom Management Strategies as Perceived by the Principals Themselves*

Profiles	Computed r-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	0.267	0.488	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Gender	0.580	0.102	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.392	0.297	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Years In Teaching Experience	0.120	0.759	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Current Position	0.267	0.488	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Relevant Training and Seminars Attended	0.905	0.047	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 25 shows the Significant Relationship between the Principal Respondents' Profile and the Extent of the Teachers' Employment of Classroom Management Strategies as Perceived by the Principals Themselves. It can be gleaned that in terms of the extent of the frequency under the principal's perception, only the relevant training and seminars attended with the p-value of 0.047 established a significant relationship to the classroom management strategies. The rest of the indicators in the profile such as age and gender, highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and the current teaching position established no significant relationship.

School principals perceived that the extent of the frequency of classroom management strategies can be learned and appreciated through attending the different relevant training and seminars (Zarowski et al., 2021; Gantalao et al., 2023). These relevant training and seminars are pertinent in adjusting the existing trends in educational practices. The challenges that emerge today are diverse. Learners have differing attitudes and behaviors due to various external factors such as the advancement of technology and the influence of different cultures due to globalization (Johler et al., 2022; Gimena et al., 2023). These challenges are brought into the classroom where teachers should find a way to augment the gap. The best remedy is to employ innovative strategies that can be learned and enhanced through relevant training and seminars attended (Egeberg et al., 2021).

Table 26. *Significant Relationship between the Principal Respondents' Profile and the Usefulness of the Classroom Management Strategies of the Teachers as Perceived by the Principals Themselves*

Profiles	Computed r-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	0.404	0.281	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Gender	0.186	0.632	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.090	0.818	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Years In Teaching Experience	0.377	0.317	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Current Position	0.295	0.440	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Relevant Training and Seminars Attended	0.380	0.313	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 26 shows the Significant Relationship between the Principal Respondents' Profile and the Usefulness of the Classroom Management Strategies of the Teachers as Perceived by the Principals Themselves. It can be gleaned that none of the demographic profiles established a significant relationship in the perception of the classroom management strategies' usefulness by the principal. This means that in terms of the usefulness of the strategies, the demographic profile of the principal does not affect how teachers employ the identified management strategies inside the classroom (Chen & Guo, 2020).

The usefulness of the classroom management strategies as perceived by the principal is crucial in creating a positive learning environment. The principal's demographic profile may not necessarily play a significant role in the usefulness of classroom management strategies. Reducing the disruption inside the classroom can be achieved when the classroom management strategies are utilized well by the teachers (Flores et al., 2023; Dionaldo et al., 2024). This should be monitored by the school principals so that teachers will consistently deliver the best quality education that the learners deserve.

Table 27. Significant Difference between the Teachers and Principals Rating Towards the Management Strategies

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Computed t-test value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Teachers' Rating Towards the Management Strategies				
Principals' Rating Towards the Management Strategies	0.680	0.516	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 27 shows the Significant Difference between the Teachers and Principals Ratings Towards the Management Strategies. The data revealed no significant difference between the teachers' and principals' ratings for classroom management strategies, with a p-value of 0.516. This accepts the null hypothesis of the study. With this, the ratings from the teacher and principal respondents are significant to understand that these ratings are not necessarily connected as several factors affect the extent of frequency and usefulness of the identified classroom management strategies (Bohol et al., 2024).

Teachers are obliged to provide quality instruction inside the classroom as indicated in the job description and stipulated in the law (Liebowitz & Portal, 2020; Layese et al., 2024). To sustain this is not a piece of cake as challenges emerge in today's era. The educational challenges and gaps in the classroom are varied and social-relative. Teachers should find a way to address these and continue to give the best learning experience. To sustain the consistency of the forwarding quality education, school principals are also obliged by law to supervise and manage the teachers. Although the results would give the impression that the ratings of the teachers and principals are not significant, the words and advice of the principal may create a difference or matter to the growth and development of the teachers' progress.

Conclusion

The years of teaching experience and relevant training and seminars in the teaching profession are tantamount to effectively utilizing classroom management strategies to create a conducive learning environment. In this study, there are identified strategies such as behavior modification, assertive discipline, incentive method, reality therapy, and distinctive method. Among these, the teachers' and principals' perceptions of the classroom management strategies' usefulness and frequency are closely alike in assertive and reality therapy. Teachers in this generation use a transformative approach to teaching wherein they are more into providing the learning needs of the students. With this, utilizing classroom management strategies should be appropriate in addressing the challenges inside the classroom where learners can attain increased productivity and the best learning experiences.

This study recommended that capturing other classroom management strategies can be determined and evaluated on how to tailor-fit the needs of the learners in this generation. Aside from behavior modification, assertive discipline, incentive methods, reality therapy, and distinctive methods, classroom management strategies that target the emotions of the learners can be explored and tested. More enhancement seminars and training should be provided to the teachers to constantly update them with the trends and the ways how to deal with the learners.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Honey Mae A. Cardines

Cerdeña Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines